

Temperature-Controlled Catalysis by Core–Shell–Satellite AuAg@pNIPAM@Ag Hybrid Microgels: A Highly Efficient Catalytic Thermo-responsive Nanoreactor

Lazaros Tzounis,^{†,‡} Manuel Doña,[§] Juan Manuel Lopez-Romero,[§] Andreas Fery,^{*,||,⊥,#} and Rafael Contreras-Caceres^{*,§,¶}

[†]Department of Materials Science & Engineering, University of Ioannina, GR-45110 Ioannina, Greece

[‡]Printed Electronic Devices of Things P.C. (PDoT), Makrinitis 122, GR-38333 Volos, Greece

[§]Departamento de Química Orgánica, Facultad de Ciencias, Universidad de Málaga, 29071 Málaga, Spain

^{||}Leibniz-Institut für Polymerforschung Dresden e.V., Hohe Str. 6, 01069 Dresden, Germany

[⊥]Physical Chemistry of Polymeric Materials, Technische Universität Dresden, 01069 Dresden, Germany

[#]Cluster of Excellence Centre for Advancing Electronics Dresden (cfaed), Technische Universität Dresden, 01062 Dresden, Germany

[¶]Department of Chemistry in Pharmaceutical Sciences, Faculty of Pharmacy, Complutense University of Madrid, Plaza Ramon y Cajal, 28040 Madrid, Spain

ABSTRACT: A novel wet-chemical protocol is reported for the synthesis of “temperature-programmable” catalytic colloids consisting of bimetallic core@shell AuAg nanoparticles encapsulated into poly(*N*-isopropylacrylamide) (pNIPAM) microgels with silver satellites (AgSTs) incorporated within the microgel structure. Spherical AuNPs of 50 nm in diameter are initially synthesized and used for growing a pNIPAM microgel shell with temperature stimulus response. A silver shell is subsequently grown on the Au core by diffusing Ag salt through the hydrophilic pNIPAM microgel (AuAg@pNIPAM microgel). The use of allylamine as a co-monomer during pNIPAM polymerization facilitates the coordination of Ag⁺ with the NH₂ nitrogen lone pair of electrons, which are reduced to Ag seeds (~14 nm) using a strong reducing agent, obtaining thus AuAg@pNIPAM@Ag hybrid microgels. The two systems are tested as catalysts toward the reduction of 4-nitrophenol (4-Nip) to 4-aminophenol (4-Amp) by NaBH₄. Both exhibit extremely sensitive temperature-dependent reaction rate constants, with the highest K_1 value of the order of 0.6 L/m² s, which is one of the highest values ever reported. The presence of plasmonic entities is confirmed by UV–vis spectroscopy. Dynamic light scattering proves the temperature responsiveness in all cases. Transmission electron microscopy and energy-dispersive X-ray (EDX) elemental mapping highlight the monodispersity of the synthesized hybrid nanostructured microgels, as well as their size and metallic composition. The amount of gold and silver in both systems is obtained by thermogravimetric analysis and the EDX spectrum. The reduction reaction kinetics is monitored by UV–vis spectroscopy at different temperatures for both catalytic systems, with the AuAg@pNIPAM@Ag microgels showing superior catalytic performance at all temperatures because of the synergistic effect of the AuAg core and the AgSTs. The principal novelty of this study lies in the “hierarchical” design of the metal–polymer–metal core@shell@satellite nanostructured colloids exhibiting synergistic capabilities of the plasmonic NPs for, among others, temperature-controlled catalytic applications.

KEYWORDS: pNIPAM microgels, thermo-responsive behavior, bimetallic nanoparticles, core@shell@satellite structure, silver satellites, heterogeneous catalysis, nanoreactors

1. INTRODUCTION

During the last decades, noble metal nanoparticles (MeNPs) such as gold, silver, and platinum have attracted extensive research interest because of their potential applications in several fields, that is, catalysis,^{1–3} photonics,^{4,5} electronics,^{6–8} and biosensing.^{9–11} As it is well-known, in the nano-size level, MeNPs exhibit size and shape-dependent unique optoelectronic properties compared to their bulk counterparts.¹² These

fascinating properties are principally caused by the localized surface plasmon resonance (LSPR) effect.^{13,14} Importantly, it is widely accepted that for nanotechnology-related applications and nano-architected devices, for example, liquid crystals,

nanotemplates, nanocatalysts, thin films, plasmonic crystals, and so forth, the precise control of the nanoparticle size, shape, and composition are crucial issues.¹⁵ For instance, smaller AuNPs exhibit higher catalytic activity because of their huge surface to volume ratio compared to bigger ones.¹⁶ Accordingly, AgNPs have been several times reported in literature as nanocatalysts in many electron-transfer chemical reactions for several reasons: (i) tunable surface plasmon and photothermal effects, (ii) excellent resistance to corrosion and air oxidation, and (iii) high surface area combined with a large number of reactive sites endowing excellent catalytic capabilities.^{17,18}

Metallic catalysts are essential in, for example, converting hazardous waste into less harmful products. Accordingly, the complete eradication of nitro aromatic compounds, usually found in water environments, without generating any hazardous byproducts via catalytic degradation, is a challenging process.^{18–20} The conversion of 4-nitrophenol (4-Nip) to 4-aminophenol (4-Amp), as well as other amino derivatives formed from the hydrogenation of nitroaromatic compounds, could have many industrial applications, including manufacturing of vital life-saving drugs, pesticides, and so forth, and maintaining a cleaner environment. More specific, 4-Nip is a refractory molecule that has negative effects on human health as well as on the environment, while 4-Amp is a raw chemical that plays an important role in, for example, the development of photographic film, etching inhibitor, hair dyeing component, and so forth. The reduction of 4-Nip to 4-Amp by BH_4^- ions has been widely used to evaluate the catalytic activity of different systems because 4-Nip displays a clear UV-vis absorption peak at 400 nm.²¹ Thus, the progress of the reaction can be monitored by the decrease in the maximum peak, and the conversion rate can be deduced from the first-order reaction kinetics.²² Therefore, the catalytic conversion of 4-Nip to 4-Amp, and its derivatives, is an ideal reaction not only to determine the catalytic activity of various MeNP catalysts, but also to shed light into necessary degradation processes for the elimination of harmful aromatic nitro derivatives found in the environment.²³

The main bottleneck of MeNPs dispersed in a specific solvent, otherwise defined as colloidal dispersions, is that they could exhibit aggregation phenomena due to their high surface energy, reducing their practical applications. This effect can induce further a large decrease of the nanoparticle's physicochemical properties, for example, catalytic activity, optical responses, sensing properties, and so forth. In order to prevent catalytic NPs from aggregation, thus obtaining stable catalysts, a stabilizer is usually employed.²⁴ However, the use of covalently bound stabilizers may block some of the crystalline lattices of the MeNP surfaces, thereby keeping inactive some of their catalytic reactive sites.²⁵ The use of a labile ligand, for example, citrate or surfactants may overcome this problem; however, still there remains the high possibility of particle aggregation during the redox reaction processes. Therefore, the experimental protocol for the synthesis of noble MeNPs with controllable particle size and long-term stability is a challenge for high-yield catalytic reactions, as well as other applications, where physicochemical reactions and mass transport phenomena occur, as for instance electrochemical plasmonic optical sensors, high performance electronics, and so forth.²⁶ Recently, some strategies have been proposed to overcome the previously mentioned aggregation problems based on the fabrication of hybrid systems composed of polymeric NPs or

inorganic material structures, where MeNPs can endow their unique properties to the resulting nanoassemblies. Such hybrid systems are able to display optical, spectroscopic, and catalytic properties supplied by the MeNPs, with the advantages of improved colloidal stability and entrapment capabilities supplied by the polymer or inorganic material used as support or shell. This approach, in the case of catalysis, not only could make available the nanocatalyst's active sites to the reaction medium increasing the amount of molecules near the catalyst surface, but also could prevent the catalyst from aggregation.

During the last years, a variety of polymeric materials such as dendrimers,²⁷ latex particles,²⁸ polymer brushes,^{29,30} and microgels³¹ have been used as MeNP supports enabling control of their colloidal stability for different purposes.³² Moreover, two-dimensional (2D) materials such as graphene³³ and clays,³⁴ as well as spherical inorganic NPs, that is, SiO_2 have been used for the immobilization of MeNPs.^{2,35} Among these 3D and 2D material supports, polymeric microgels represent an intriguing candidate because of both their stimuli-responsive capability, as well as their unique cross-linked network structures with extended pore networks allowing the possibility to accumulate certain molecules, but also the potential of in situ nucleation and growth of NPs.³⁶ At the same time, the charged polymer surface can effectively hinder NPs from aggregation and thus preserve and guarantee their thermal and chemical stability.³⁷ Importantly, microgel size and the swollen capability can be adjusted by varying the amount of monomer, and the cross-linking density, as well as the incorporation of co-monomers during polymerization that offers the possibility to include certain functional groups into the microgel network.^{1,38,39} Apart from this, the microgel porous structures facilitate the rapid diffusion of small reactant molecules, which is a critical parameter in heterogeneous catalytic reactions. Consequently, the connection of the stimuli-responsive behavior of microgels with optical, spectroscopic, and catalytic properties of embedded MeNPs leads to the generation of highly stabilized stimuli-responsive nanomaterials to be used as catalytic micro- and nanoreactors.⁴⁰

Poly(*N*-isopropylacrylamide) (pNIPAM) is by far the most studied thermoresponsive microgel that undergoes a reversible volume phase transition (VPT) in response to temperature with a lower critical solution temperature (LCST) around 32 °C in water. This means that the microgel swells by the incorporation of solvent molecules (e.g., water) below LCST because of the formation of H-bonds between water and acrylamide groups. In a contrary way, above the LCST, the solvent is expelled because of the breakage of H-bonds, and this causes the microgel to collapse because of the high hydrophobicity of the methylene groups. The fabrication of hybrid systems composed of MeNPs and pNIPAM allows fabricating systems on different structures. For example, a particle core encapsulated by a pNIPAM shell is normally denoted as a core@shell structure.⁴¹ MeNPs incorporated and distributed within the microgel network are named as core@satellites structures.⁴² Indeed, these hybrid microgels could exhibit, in response to external temperature, tunable catalytic activity. Indeed, as was mentioned, pNIPAM microgels also exhibit an amphiphilic behavior with a hydrophilic nature and good dispersability in water below LCST, while they show a hydrophobic nature above LCST, allowing them to be dispersed in an organic solvent or enabling the recyclability of the material by temperature control.

It is important to mention that AgNPs are more interesting compared to AuNPs in terms of plasmonic and catalytic purposes. This is attributed to the higher energy of the interband transition, leading to a minimum damping of the plasmon, thus improving electron-transfer chemical reactions. Thus, concerning the synthesis of hybrid colloidal systems AgNPs and pNIPAM in the structure, Liz-Marzán and coworkers^{43–45} developed a general method to encapsulate bimetallic AuAg nanoparticles (AuAgNPs) of different sizes and shapes within pNIPAM microgels resulting in hybrid core@shell structures. However, to this colloidal structure, only surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy (SERS) investigations were performed. In general, for colloidal systems containing MeNPs, the catalytic activity for AgNPs is expressed using the apparent rate constant (K_{app}), which is basically a value related with the decrease of the reactants concentration during the catalytic reaction. However, for a qualitative comparison of the catalytic activity, K_1 is a more appropriate parameter. This constant is defined as the apparent rate constant (K_{app}) normalized to the specific surface area (S) of metal NPs. In this context, Ballauf et al. reported on core@satellites structures based on polystyrene@pNIPAM core structures with immobilized silver satellites (AgSTs), which were used as nanoreactors for the reduction of 4-Nip. They found K_1 values dependent on temperatures, and their highest K_1 value was $5.2 \times 10^{-2} \text{ L/m}^2 \text{ s}$.^{31,46} More recently, Liu et al. synthesized core@satellites pNIPAM@Ag hybrid microgels. Different from the previous case, they found that the catalytic activity could be tuned over four distinct stages of change versus temperature, with the highest K_{app} values from 7.0×10^{-4} to $2.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$.⁴⁷ Lü et al. prepared Ag nanoclusters using a thermoresponsive copolymer ligand (CPL) consisting of 5-(2-methacryloyloxyethyl)oxymethyl-8-quinolinol (MQ) and *N*-isopropylacrylamide units, which showed a size-dependent and thermoresponsive catalytic activity toward 4-Nip reduction. Surprisingly, these authors reported that above 32 °C, the catalytic activity of the as-prepared CPL capped with Ag nanocluster was reduced because of the shrinkage of NIPAM,⁴⁸ with K_{app} values ranging from 5.0×10^{-3} to $2.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ s g}^{-1}$. Zhu et al. used core@satellites pNIPAM@Au nanocomposite hydrogels for the reduction of *o*-nitroaniline, obtaining a highest K_{app} around $2.8 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$.⁴⁹ More recently, Lu et al. prepared catalytic active bimetallic Au–Pt nanorods onto thermoresponsive core@shell PS@NIPAM microgels.⁵⁰ The hybrid system showed enhanced catalytic activity because of the synergistic effect of bimetallic NPs, obtaining K_1 values between 8.2×10^{-2} and $0.21 \text{ L/m}^2 \text{ s}$.

Concerning the catalytic behavior of similar previously reported nanohybrid systems, Carregal-Romero et al. fabricated ~60 nm spherical gold nanoparticles coated with pNIPAM (Au@pNIPAM).¹ Authors investigated the electron-transfer reaction between hexacyanoferrate(III) to sodium borohydride. The catalytic behavior is similar to that found by us. They found an increase of K_{apps} at the vicinity of the LCST (Arrhenius-like behavior), a decrease during the phase transition, and increases after microgel collapse (Arrhenius-like behavior). The only difference is that the double Arrhenius-like behavior was obtained at lower temperatures. This difference may be produced because the molecule used for the catalysis is different. They used $\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$, which is a smaller and more polar molecule compared with 4-NP (a bigger molecule that contains an aromatic ring). Lu et al. performed the catalytic reduction of 4-NP with NaBH_4 and

they fabricated a raspberry-like colloidal system.⁵⁰ They synthesized pNIPAM microgels as a core decorated with gold nanorods (containing Pt nanoparticles) on the surface. In this situation, the catalytic reaction is principal or totally produced on the pNIPAM surface, where the Au–Pt particles are accumulated. Wu et al. also investigated the reduction of 4-NP by NaBH_4 ; however, they fabricated a thermoresponsive yolk–shell system.⁵¹ These authors included a theoretical model for the analysis of the kinetic behavior, and they took into account the pathway between the microgel and the Au surface. Recently, Li et al. developed a bimetallic AuAg core encapsulated by a pNIPAM shell.⁵² The bimetallic core was prepared by a galvanic replacement reaction between Ag NPs and HAuCl_4 . However, after a detailed observation of the transmission electron microscopy (TEM) images, it can be seen that the bimetallic nanoparticles are not homogeneously surrounded by a pNIPAM shell. Consequently, by the noncoated areas, the reactants do not diffuse through the pNIPAM network, and probably this circumstance affects the catalytic behavior. Li et al. investigated the effect of temperature on the rate of 4-NP reduction in pNIPAM-co-AA@Ag systems.⁵³ The catalytic effect for this core@satellite system has double Arrhenius-like behavior with the highest K_{app} value at 32 °C. Another nanocomposite structured system with the maximum K_{app} value obtained at 32 °C was reported by Lü et al.⁴⁸ These authors fabricated well-defined silver nanoclusters by using a temperature-responsive CPL containing MQ and *N*-isopropylacrylamide (NIPAM) units. More recently, Hellweg et al. reported the incorporation of AgSTs into core@shell microgels.⁵⁴ These structures are formed by a core fabricated with NIPAM, *N*-isopropylmethacrylamide or *N*-*n*-propylacrylamide as a core (co-polymerized with acrylic acid), and a shell formed by poly-*N*-*n*-propylacrylamide in every case. In these systems, Ag nanoparticles are included into the polymeric core, and the polymeric shell provides colloidal stability and controls the diffusion of reactants. However, these colloidal systems do not have a bimetallic AuAg core encapsulated by a pNIPAM shell (AuAg@pNIPAM). Roa et al. has recently reported a review focused in catalysis performed by metallic nanohybrid particles.⁴⁰ In this review, authors divided active carriers as yolk–shell, core–shell, as well as nanoparticles randomly embedded into the microgel. They include theory and model for the diffusion and precise kinetics of reactants in different reported systems. Authors conclude that the architecture of the nanohybrid systems is critical for the thermocatalytic behavior.

Herein, spherical 50 nm AuNPs encapsulated within a thermoresponsive pNIPAM–allylamine copolymer microgel have been initially synthesized. Then, an Ag shell has been grown on the Au core obtaining bimetallic AuAg@pNIPAM microgels. The presence of allylamine was exploited in order to coordinate Ag^+ ions, which were reduced to Ag satellites within the microgel structure (AuAg@pNIPAM@Ag microgels). Particle size and surface plasmon resonance (SPR) characteristics in the resultant plasmonic microgels in response to temperature were analyzed by dynamic light scattering (DLS) and UV–vis spectroscopy. TEM images and energy-dispersive X-ray (EDX) elemental mapping analysis demonstrated the successful fabrication of hybrid microgels, as well as the growth of AgSTs within the pNIPAM shell. The amount of silver and gold in each hybrid system was determined by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) and EDX investigations. The catalytic activity for both AuAg@pNIPAM and AuAg@pNIPAM@Ag

Figure 1. (a) Schematic illustration of the synthetic route for the fabrication of hybrid nanostructured microgels and (b) catalytic improvement due to the "by-design" synergistic mechanism of the AuAg core and AgSTs.

was studied by the reduction of 4-Nip to 4-Amp in the presence of NaBH₄, and it was found to be remarkably increased after the immobilization of AgSTs. The effect of the reaction temperature on the reduction rate was also investigated. The highest K_1 value was found to be 0.6 L/m² s, obtained for the AuAg@pNIPAM@Ag microgel system at 44 °C. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first reported synthesis as well as the thermoresponsive catalytic investigation of hybrid nanostructured microgels formed by a bimetallic AuAg core, a pNIPAM microgel shell, and AgSTs. Thus, the principal novelty aspects of this work are as follows: (i) the presence of a controllable silver shell surrounded by a pNIPAM microgel providing enhanced catalytic properties compared to a pure Au core, (ii) the immobilization of AgSTs that induce a synergistic catalytic mechanism together with the AuAg core, and (iii) the achievement of a thermoresponsive behavior, resulting in temperature-programmable catalytic nanoreactors with trapping capabilities and tunable hydrophilic to hydrophobic behavior. The latter contribution suggests that the hybrid microgels could be ideal candidates for other heterogeneous catalytic reactions in water treatment or organic media. "Indeed, there is a clear evidence that the growth of both the Ag shell and AgSTs can result in a temperature-controlled plasmonic coupling, thus obtaining colloidal systems with improved plasmonic applications in SERS, optical sensors, and so forth."

2. EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

2.1. Materials. Ascorbic acid (AA, 99%), cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB, ≥99%), 3-butenoic acid (3-BA, 97%), allylamine (allyl, 98%), silver nitrate (AgNO₃, ≥99%), sodium borohydride (NaBH₄, ≥96%), and *N*-isopropylacrylamide (NIPAM, 97%) were supplied by Sigma-Aldrich. HAuCl₄·3H₂O, trisodium

citrate dihydrate, and sodium hydroxide (NaOH) were supplied as well by Sigma. *N,N'*-Methylenebisacrylamide (BIS, ≥99.5%) and 4-nitrophenol (4-C₆H₅NO₃) were supplied by Fluka. 2,2'-Azobis(2-methylpropionamide)dihydrochloride (V50, 97%) was supplied by Acros Organics. All reactants were used without further purification. Water was purified using a Milli-Q system (Millipore).

2.2. Synthesis of Au@pNIPAM Microgels. Prior to use, all glassware were cleaned with a 3:1 v/v acidic solution consisting of hydrochloric/nitric acid (36 and 68%, respectively) and then rinsed copiously with Milli-Q water. The encapsulation of AuNPs within pNIPAM was performed in a two-step process. First, AuNPs with a mean diameter of ~50 nm were prepared through a modification of the seeded-mediated growth method.⁵⁵ This method is based on the reduction of HAuCl₄ with 3-BA using CTAB-stabilized AuNP as seeds (ca. 15 nm, previously prepared by citrate reduction), in the presence of 0.015 M CTAB. Second, the pNIPAM polymer shell was grown by free radical polymerization in the presence of the previously synthesized vinyl-terminated AuNPs. In order to achieve that, Au colloidal dispersion (10 mL, 5 mM in terms of Au) was heated to 70 °C under a N₂ flow. Then, the polymerization was carried out by introducing a monomer mixture composed by NIPAM (0.1698 g), the cross-linker BIS (23.2 mg, 10% in mols), and allylamine (7.5 μL, 8% in mol) under a N₂ flow. After 15 min at 70 °C, the polymerization was started by adding 2,2'-azobis(2-methylpropionamide)dihydrochloride (100 μL, 0.1 M). After 15 min, the reddish solution became turbid, then the N₂ flow was removed and the reaction was allowed to proceed for 2 h at 70 °C. The mixture was left to cool down at room temperature under magnetic stirring. In order to remove free microgels, as well as oligomers and/or residual monomers produced during the polymerization process, the final colloidal sample was diluted with water (50 mL) and centrifuged (30 min at 4500 rpm). This step was repeated five times, and the final resulting pellet was redispersed in 10 mL of Milli-Q water.

2.3. Synthesis of Core@Shell AuAg@pNIPAM Microgels. The synthesis of AuAg@pNIPAM microgel particles was performed

following a previously reported protocol.⁵⁵ Initially, to 10 mL of 0.4 M glycine buffer solution at pH 9.5 (adjusted by adding 1 M NaOH) containing the previous Au microgels (0.25 mM in terms of Au) and CTAB (50 mM), first 148 μL of 29.4 mM AgNO_3 and 87.2 μL of 100 mM AA were added under magnetic stirring (~ 400 rpm). After 30 min, the particle dispersion was centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 30 min. The supernatant was discarded and the pellet was redispersed in 10 mL of Milli-Q water.

2.4. Synthesis of Core@Shell@Satellites AuAg@pNIPAM@Ag Microgels. In 10 mL of the previously prepared AuAg@pNIPAM microgel dispersion, 25 μL of 29.4 mM AgNO_3 was added at room temperature and medium magnetic stirring. The solution was kept under these conditions during 30 min to allow a homogeneous coordination of Ag^+ ions with the amine groups from allylamine. Then, the reduction of coordinated Ag^+ ions was achieved by adding 95 μL of 50 mM NaBH_4 at room temperature and vigorous magnetic stirring. After 5 min, the solution was centrifuged at 5500 rpm during 30 min. The supernatant was discarded, and the pellet was redispersed in 10 mL of Milli-Q water. This cleaning process was repeated twice.

2.5. Characterization Methods. All UV-vis spectra were recorded using a Cary 50 scanning spectrophotometer (Varian, USA) with an incorporated xenon flash lamp by using a standard quartz cuvette (path length 1 cm). DLS was performed using a Malvern Zetasizer Nano S (Malvern Instruments, Malvern UK) using a detection angle of 173° . The intensity-averaged particle diameter and the polydispersity index values were calculated from cumulant-type analysis. Data were acquired after 5 min of sample dispersion and stabilization at each temperature (from 25 to 44 $^\circ\text{C}$), with all measurements repeated three-fold. FTIR spectra were recorded by using a Nicolet IR200 FT-IR spectrometer. All the spectra were acquired by signal averaging of 512 scans. Approximately 1.0 mg of neat or both AuAg@pNIPAM and AuAg@pNIPAM@Ag particles, and 100 μL of pure allylamine, were pressed together with 100 mg of crystalline KBr to form pellets. TEM investigations were performed by using a JEOL JEM 1400 (JEOL, Japan) operating at an acceleration voltage of 80 kV. Tomography images were acquired on a Talos F200X at an acceleration voltage of 200 kV. 3D-reconstruction of the tomography was carried out using the proprietary software. High-angle annular dark field (HAADF) scanning TEM and EDX mappings were conducted by using a FEI Talos F200X (FEI, USA) equipped with an EDX detector samples for TEM were prepared by adding 10 μL of each suspension on a Cu grid with a carbon support membrane, followed by drying. TGA analysis was performed by using a Mettler Toledo STAR system. After drying in the vacuum overnight, the composites were heated to 800 $^\circ\text{C}$ with a heating rate of 10 $^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ under N_2 . The catalytic activity was proven quantitatively via the reduction of 4-Nip to 4-Amp in excess of NaBH_4 as a model reaction. In a typical experiment, 0.5 mL of a freshly prepared aqueous solution of NaBH_4 (60 mM) was mixed with 2.0 mL of 4-nitrophenol aqueous solution (0.1 mM) in a quartz cuvette (path length 1 cm). To this mixture, a constant amount of 50 μL from AuAg@pNIPAM (0.5 mg/mL) and AuAg@pNIPAM@Ag (0.25 mg/mL) dispersed in Milli-Q water was added, and the reaction mixture was monitored immediately by successive UV-vis spectra taken every 60 s in the range of 280–500 nm. The catalytic reaction was performed at 25, 28, 32, 36, 40, and 44 $^\circ\text{C}$. The rate constants of the catalytically activated reactions using each system were determined by measuring the change in intensity of the peak at 400 nm with time. Figure 1a shows the synthetic protocol followed to fabricate the hybrid thermoresponsive catalytic nanocolloids, while Figure 1b illustrates the innovation of our work combining bimetallic AuAg core and AgSTs reaching enhanced and synergistic catalytic performance compared with previously reported systems.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Electron Microscopy Investigations. Figure 2 shows representative TEM images of Au@pNIPAM, AuAg@pNIPAM and AuAg@pNIPAM@Ag systems as a direct evidence for the formation of metal-hybrid microgels. TEM

Figure 2. Representative TEM images of (A) Au@pNIPAM, (B) AuAg@pNIPAM, (C,D) AuAg@pNIPAM@Ag hybrid microgels at two different magnifications.

investigations revealed the morphology and size characteristics of the synthesized microgels. It should be noted that the microgel sizes previously estimated by DLS are larger than those obtained by TEM because the former reflects the swollen microgel size in solution, while the latter reveals the morphology of completely collapsed microgel in the dry state, after drying on the TEM grid. Figure 2A shows a hybrid structure composed by the AuNP core encapsulated by a microgel shell in a typical core@shell structure. A high contrast of Au spheres embedded within low contrast monodispersed spherical microgel particles is observed. Dimension particle analysis performed by measuring 100 AuNPs reveals a core diameter of 48.6 ± 3.4 nm (Figure S1A). Figure 2B shows the TEM image of AuAg@pNIPAM microgel particles. The same core@shell morphology structured as a metal core encapsulated by a microgel shell is observed. In this case, dimension analysis provides an average particle size of 63.6 ± 5.9 nm (Figure S1B). This means that an Ag shell of about 15 nm was formed around the Au core. Finally, Figures 2C,D exhibits the nano-architected hierarchical AuAg@pNIPAM@Ag system. The images show the presence of AgSTs into the pNIPAM microgel network. Particle size distribution corresponding to the AgSTs is included in Figure S1C, while the measured mean diameter was 14.6 ± 4.8 nm. It is important to mention that because TEM images are obtained from dried samples, it is difficult to quantify whether the NPs are seeded only from the surface of the microgel or from the interior of the microgel matrix. However, from the images of dried hybrid microgels, we can qualitatively say that AgSTs are distributed uniformly. In order to confirm the position of the Ag satellites in the pNIPAM microgel, we include 3D tomography investigations for an AuAg@pNIPAM@Ag sample structured as a spherical 100 nm core coated by a 15 nm Ag shell encapsulated by pNIPAM containing Ag satellites (Supporting Information Videos S1 and S2). As is observed, the Ag satellites are well-distributed within the microgel network and are not located on the pNIPAM surface. It may be possible that in the case of

Figure 3. HAADF-TEM image for (A) AuAg@pNIPAM and (E) AuAg@pNIPAM@Ag microgels. (B,F) EDX elemental mapping of mixed silver and gold for the two systems. (C,D) EDX elemental mapping of silver and gold for AuAg@pNIPAM, and (G,H) EDX elemental mapping of silver and gold for AuAg@pNIPAM@Ag microgels, respectively.

AgSTs, a majority of seeding prefer to take place in the loosely cross-linked shell regions of microgel, which have a higher available surface area than the tightly cross-linked core.

Figure S2 shows also a more detailed TEM characterization of the three different systems. It is important to note that in Figure S2C, the amounts of AgNO_3 and NaBH_4 were duplicated compared with the synthesis followed in the experimental section. As it is observed, some AgSTs are connected because of the increase in the particle size. In conclusion, a Ag shell on the Au surface is obtained when a mild reducing agent (AA) is introduced into the growth solution. It is important to remark that AA has not enough redox potential necessary to reduce Ag^+ to Ag^0 . In order to increase the redox potential, a pH higher than 7.5 is necessary.⁵⁶ In our case, we used a glycine buffer solution at $\text{pH} > 7.5$. By using these soft conditions, nucleation is not produced, and Ag ions are able to diffuse through the pNIPAM network until the gold surface, where the reduction to Ag is achieved, thus obtaining a core@shell structure.^{30,55} However, Ag^+ ions, after being coordinated with NH_2 groups from allylamine, generate satellites when a strong reducing agent is introduced into the mixture. In our case, a certain amount of NaBH_4 is used, thus resulting in Ag nucleation instead of an Ag shell. A better characterization concerning the composition of the three systems was achieved via HAADF-TEM and EDX elemental mapping, as shown in Figure S3 for the Au@pNIPAM microgels, and Figure 3 for AuAg@pNIPAM and AuAg@pNIPAM@Ag systems. For the first one, the silver shell and the gold core can be easily distinguished by overlaying the elemental maps of both metals (Figure 3B). A homogeneous Ag shell of about 17 nm surrounding the gold core is observed, in good agreement with previous measurements. Interestingly, for the AuAg@pNIPAM@Ag system, apart from the previously observed core@shell configuration of Au coated by Ag, a plethora of AgSTs can be distinguished (Figure 3E,F), supporting the core@shell@satellite structure. It is important to emphasize that bimetallic core@shell AuAgNPs have been previously reported, even located in the center of pNIPAM microgels, but this AuAg@Ag microgel is the first reported system with core@shell@satellite architecture that shows also thermoresponsive capabilities. In order to 3D tomography.

3.2. Thermosensitivity of Hybrid Microgels Using DLS Analysis. The hydrodynamic diameter (D_h), as well as the swollen-shrinking variations of Au@pNIPAM (black squares), AuAg@pNIPAM (red circles), and AuAg@pNIPAM@Ag (blue triangles) hybrid microgels as a function of temperature (25–44 °C) are shown in Figure 4A,B, respectively. The

Figure 4. (A) Temperature dependence of the D_h , and (B) shrinking ratio for the Au@pNIPAM (black squares), AuAg@pNIPAM (red circles), and AuAg@pNIPAM@Ag (blue triangles) hybrid microgels.

shrinking ratio (the inverse of the swelling ratio) is defined as the ratio between the volume of the particle in the swollen state (at 25 °C) and the volume of the particle at each temperature [$\beta = V_{\text{swollen}}(25\text{ °C})/V(T)$].⁴¹ As was expected, the temperature-induced swelling and shrinkage degree of Au@pNIPAM (black square) and AuAg@pNIPAM (red circles) were similar. Specifically, Au@pNIPAM and AuAg@pNIPAM microgels gave a D_h value of ~342 nm at 25 °C, with a significant measured decrease to ~240 nm in the collapsed state at 44 °C. Indeed, the shrinking ratio was ~2.7 in both cases. However, the AuAg@pNIPAM@Ag system shows reduced swelling behavior, with a decreased shrinkage ratio compared to the other two systems. The particle size at the swollen state was measured in ~345 nm, and after temperature was raised to 44 °C, the D_h value was reduced to ~260 nm. Interestingly, the system containing AgSTs produced a reduced microgel collapse compared with the previous systems, with a shrinking ratio of ~2.2. The most probable scenario explaining this behavior is that the AgSTs incorporated into the pNIPAM cross-linked network reduce the microgel's swelling–deswelling capabilities. More specifically, the presence of AgSTs hinders the chain mobility during microgel collapse, resulting in a lower swelling capacity, thus adding a new contribution

Figure 5. UV-vis spectra of (A) Au@pNIPAM, (B) AuAg@pNIPAM, and (C) AuAg@pNIPAM@Ag hybrid microgels obtained at 25 °C (black line) and 50 °C (red line), respectively. (D) FTIR spectra of AuAg@pNIPAM (black line) and AuAg@pNIPAM@Ag (red line) particles.

that opposes the microgel collapse. Furthermore, we also hypothesize that because of the hydrophilic nature of AgSTs (covered by $\text{-BH}_4\text{-}$ anions), they could be solvated by water molecules, thus avoiding the fact that the microgel efficiently expels the water molecules above LCST. This is a possible explanation to confirm that the AgSTs are distributed within the entire pNIPAM microgel.

3.3. SPR Properties of the Hybrid Microgels and FTIR.

Figure 5A–C shows the UV-vis spectra for the Au@pNIPAM, AuAg@pNIPAM, and AuAg@pNIPAM@Ag microgel systems exhibiting the presence of LSPR peaks for all systems, as well as their temperature-dependent plasmonic behavior. The UV-vis spectrum of the Au@pNIPAM microgel particles (Figure 5A) revealed a maximum absorption peak for Au located at 540 nm at 25 °C, which is displaced to 552 nm at 50 °C (12 nm shift). For the AuAg@pNIPAM microgel system (Figure 5B), the UV-vis spectrum showed a minimum at ca. 320 nm, characteristic of the interband transition of the Ag.⁵¹ Both Au (507 nm) and Ag (403 nm) plasmonic peaks were detected, being the Au core the main plasmonic contributor in the spectra due to its 50 nm size compared to the Ag shell of 15 nm (data and images will be given in the TEM section). It should be mentioned that the Au LSPR peak in Figure 5B shifted to lower wavelengths because of the higher excitation cross-section of Ag compared with Au. It is important to note that the Au plasmon band for bimetallic core@shell AuAg particles displaces the Au plasmon band position to shorter wavelengths. The origin of such displacement is assigned to the differences in the complex dielectric function of Ag and Au, which results in a variation of the effective dielectric function of the bimetallic core@shell nanoparticles.^{30,55,56} Indeed, Au showed a red shift of the plasmon peak by the increase of temperature, being the plasmon band for the Au located at 507 nm at 25 °C, and at 518 nm in the collapsed state (11 nm shift). The sensitivity of the displacement in a bimetallic core@shell AuAgNPs depends on the effective dielectric function of

the bimetallic core@shell nanoparticles.^{57–59} This displacement fits with those previously reported,⁵⁵ where a displacement in the Au surface plasmon band of 17 nm was found for AuAg@pNIPAM particles formed by a 64 nm Au core and a 40 nm Ag shell. The Au plasmon band is shifted even if the microgel is not directly attached on the Au surface. Finally, the UV-vis spectrum for AuAg@pNIPAM@Ag particles (Figure 5C) showed a more intense minimum at ca. 320 nm compared with that for the AuAg@pNIPAM microgel system and a more blue shifted plasmon band position for Au@pNIPAM (500 nm). In the AuAg@pNIPAM@Ag system, the concomitant red shift of the Au produced above the LCST was 11 nm, (511 nm at 50 °C), equal to that for the previous AuAg@pNIPAM case. Indeed, because of the presence of the Ag satellites, there is a red shift of 4 nm for the Ag plasmon band and fits with that found for Fe_3O_4 @pNIPAM@Ag particles.^{60,61} The red shift observed for all systems could be ascribed to the local refractive index increase resulting from water expulsion produced above the VPT of the pNIPAM microgel, as has been interpreted in other similar studies.^{55,60} UV-vis spectroscopy has been proved to be a convenient technique for monitoring the shift of the LSPR band due to the change in the spatial distribution of AgNPs. Thus, another plausible mechanism to explain the red shift especially for the Ag LSPR of the AuAg@pNIPAM@Ag system is that the shrinkage of thermoresponsive pNIPAM microgels above LCST could reduce the distance between the embedded AgNPs causing plasmonic coupling among them, and resulting in the red shift of the plasmon peak.²³ However, we consider that this phenomenon is not produced, as the shift in the plasmon band was the same in AuAg@pNIPAM microgels, without AgSTs. From the above, it can be concluded that the optical properties of Au, Ag shell and AgSTs incorporated within pNIPAM microgels can be regulated by respective temperature changes, yielding highly thermoresponsive plasmonic nanocolloids for potential use in temperature-modulated catalysis, as in this

Figure 6. Corresponding plots of $\ln(C_t/C_0)$ vs time t toward the reduction reaction and the demonstration of K_{app} over the various temperatures used, respectively.

study, as well as, for example, in SERS or biomedical applications.

We have performed FTIR spectroscopy for AuAg@pNIPAM and AuAg@pNIPAM@Ag particles, as well as for pure allylamine (Figures S4 and S5, respectively). The FTIR spectra show the band corresponding to the antisymmetric and symmetric peak of the C–H bond associated to aliphatic alkanes at 2923 and 2852 cm^{-1} , respectively, in all cases. For the system without AgSTs (AuAg@pNIPAM), the FTIR spectrum includes the peaks at 3424 and 3315 cm^{-1} , which are attributed to the stretching vibration of the NH_2 groups, as well as the peaks located at 1646 and 1540 cm^{-1} , attributed to the bending vibration of the NH_2 groups from allylamine. If we compare with the FT-IR spectrum of the system with incorporated Ag satellites (AuAg@pNIPAM@Ag), the absorptions peaks from allylamine at 3424 and 3315 cm^{-1} as well as the absorptions peak at 1646 and 1540 cm^{-1} were weakened at a certain extent because of the interaction between the Ag satellites with some of the NH_2 groups from allylamine presented into the microgel network. These results fit with those found by Zhang et al. for FTIR analysis concerning P(St-NIPAM)/P(NIPAM-co-MMA) microgels and P(St-NIPAM)/P(MMA-co-NIPAM)/PPy-Ag composites.⁶²

3.4. Temperature-Controlled Catalytic Reduction of 4-Nitrophenol to 4-Aminophenol by the Hybrid Thermoresponsive Microgels. In order to evaluate quantitatively the catalytic efficiency of AuAg@pNIPAM and AuAg@pNIPAM@Ag hybrid microgels, the catalytic reduction of 4-Nip to 4-Amp with an excess of NaBH_4 was employed as a reliable model reaction.² Recently, nitrophenols and their derivatives have been found to be one of the most refractory pollutants that can be found in industrial wastewaters, thus becoming a great threat for the environment.⁶³ At the same time, the reduction of 4-Nip is important in the production of

industrial raw materials apart from the elimination of pollution. Although the reduction of 4-Nip to 4-Amp using NaBH_4 is thermodynamically favorable (E_0 for 4-Nip/4-Amp = -0.76 V and $\text{H}_3\text{BO}_3/\text{BH}_4^- = -1.33$ V vs normal hydrogen electrode), the presence of a kinetic barrier due to the large potential difference between donor and acceptor molecules decreases the feasibility of this reaction. In addition, this kinetic barrier is realized also due to the mutually repelling negative ions of Nip and BH_4^- . Therefore, the reduction cannot proceed unmediated. Metal NPs can facilitate an electron relay from the electron donor BH_4^- ions (reductant) to the acceptor 4-nitrophenolate (oxidant) ions, overcoming the kinetic barrier and efficiently catalyze the reduction of 4-Nip to 4-Amp.⁶⁴ A typical UV–vis spectrum of 4-Nip aqueous solution shows a distinct absorption maximum peak at ~ 317 nm. Upon the addition of NaBH_4 , the light yellow color of 4-Nip changes to yellow-green and the 4-Nip peak is immediately red-shifted to 400 nm because of the formation of 4-nitrophenolate ions in the alkaline medium caused by NaBH_4 .

The progress of our catalytic reaction was evaluated quantitatively by monitoring the changes of the UV–vis absorption spectra of 4-nitrophenolate ions as a function of time (60 s). As was mentioned in the **Experimental Section**, we added 50 μL of an AuAg@pNIPAM microgel dispersion at 0.05 mg/mL and 50 μL of an AuAg@pNIPAM@Ag microgel system at 0.025 mg/mL into the 4-Nip/ NaBH_4 reaction mixture containing 2.0 mL 4-Nip (0.1 mM) and 500 μL NaBH_4 (60 mM).⁶⁵ As a control experiment, the catalytic activity of bare pNIPAM microgels was evaluated. After a time period of 6 h, no change of the nitrophenolate anions peak intensity was observed confirming the catalytic role of AuAg core and AgSTs. After the addition of each of the hybrid catalytic systems at each temperature tested, the reduction of 4-Nip by NaBH_4 and its conversion to 4-Amp was measured.

Table 1. Summary of the Catalytic Activity of the Two Different Microgel Systems toward the Reduction of 4-Nip to 4-Amp by NaBH₄ at Different Temperatures

sample ID	amount (μg)	temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	calculated rate constant, K_{app} (s^{-1})	calculated K_1 ($\text{L}/\text{m}^2 \text{ s}$)
AuAg@pNIPAM	0.98	25	5.7×10^{-3}	0.18
AuAg@pNIPAM	0.98	28	6.3×10^{-3}	0.31
AuAg@pNIPAM	0.98	32	8.5×10^{-3}	0.42
AuAg@pNIPAM	0.98	36	4.2×10^{-3}	0.21
AuAg@pNIPAM	0.98	40	3.3×10^{-3}	0.16
AuAg@pNIPAM	0.98	44	3.8×10^{-3}	0.19
AuAg@pNIPAM@Ag	0.98	25	8.3×10^{-3}	0.30
AuAg@pNIPAM@Ag	0.98	28	11.2×10^{-3}	0.40
AuAg@pNIPAM@Ag	0.98	32	13.3×10^{-3}	0.48
AuAg@pNIPAM@Ag	0.98	36	7.3×10^{-3}	0.26
AuAg@pNIPAM@Ag	0.98	40	4.7×10^{-3}	0.17
AuAg@pNIPAM@Ag	0.98	44	16.4×10^{-3}	0.60

Accordingly, the intensity of the peak at 400 nm gradually dropped with time accompanied by a concomitant appearance of a new peak at 295 nm indicating the formation 4-Amp. Figure S5 represents the time-dependent UV-vis spectra recorded at regular intervals of 60 s for the reduction reaction performed at 25, 28, 32, 36, 40, and 44 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, using the AuAg@pNIPAM microgel system as the reaction thermoresponsive catalyst. As is observed, the intensity of the peak at 400 nm gradually dropped with time accompanied by a concomitant appearance of a new peak at 295 nm, indicating the formation 4-Amp. The data imply that the reaction terminates within different time frames upon different reaction temperatures, consistent with the disappearance of the yellow color of 4-Nip at the end of each reaction. Figure S6 displays the time-dependent reduction of 4-Nip using the AuAg@pNIPAM@Ag system. These results indicate that AuAg@pNIPAM@Ag microgels effectively catalyze the reaction, however, at significantly lower reaction times compared to AuAg core-only microgels for all the reaction temperatures tested. Because the concentration of NaBH₄ greatly exceeds that of 4-Nip as well as the microgel concentration, the reduction rates can be assumed to be dependent only on the concentration of 4-Nip and independent of the NaBH₄ concentration, which can be considered constant.

Taking into account the aforementioned assumption, the apparent reaction rate constants (K_{app}) for the catalytic reduction can be evaluated by studying the pseudo-first-order kinetics with respect to 4-Nip concentration as follows⁶⁶

$$-\ln(C_t/C_0) = k_{\text{app}}t \quad (1)$$

where K_{app} is the apparent rate constant of the catalytic reaction, C_t stands for the concentration at time t , and C_0 is the original concentration at time 0 of the 4-Nip solution, respectively. The C_t and C_0 values were represented by the corresponding A_t and A_0 values from the UV-vis spectra. Specifically, A_t stands for absorbance at time t and A_0 for absorbance at time 0, which was taken as the time at 60 s corresponding to the second absorbance peak at 400 nm because of relatively small "induction times" observed at the beginning of each reaction.⁶⁷

As a result, the K_{app} (s^{-1}) values were calculated from the corresponding slopes, which can be determined from the linear fits of the $\ln(A_t/A_0)$ versus t plots. Both systems exhibited very small induction period times of less than 60 s under all temperatures tested. This fact indicates that the diffusion and mass transfer of 4-Nip and BH₄⁻ toward the microgel volume

and the silver nanoparticle adsorption is efficiently facilitated compared to other pNIPAM-metal NP hybrid systems found in literature for the 4-Nip reduction, with up to 7 min of induction periods reported.²³ Figure 6A represents the $\ln(A_t/A_0)$ versus time at different temperatures using AuAg@pNIPAM microgels as catalyst particles. We can confirm that the K_{app} possess the highest value ($8.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$) at 32 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, and therefore, the shortest time required for the complete conversion of 4-Nip to 4-Amp (540 s). Figure 6B shows the K_{app} values as a function of temperature, demonstrating the potential applicability of our hybrid system for temperature-modulated catalytic performance. Figure 6C shows the $\ln(A_t/A_0)$ in function of time at several temperatures for AuAg@pNIPAM@Ag particles. In this case, the highest value and shortest time needed for the complete conversion of 4-Nip to 4-Amp at 44 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ ($16.4 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$). Figure 6D includes the K_{app} values as a function of the different reaction temperatures for the AuAg@pNIPAM@Ag microgels. From all the spectra concerning both systems, it can be concluded that (i) the intensity of the peak at 400 nm decreases gradually during the catalytic reaction but with a different K_{app} (as supported by Figure 6A,C), and (ii) it is apparent that the catalytic activity can be modulated by temperature because of the volume transition of the thermosensitive pNIPAM microgels. Consequently, the extreme temperature-sensitive microgels are capable of serving as "smart nanoreactors" for the catalytic reduction of 4-Nip to 4-Amp. All the plots shown in Figure 6A,C present a good linear relation between $\ln(A_t/A_0)$ and time t , for almost 90% of the reactions at different temperatures for each catalytic system. Figure 6B,D demonstrates the differences of the reaction rate constants at different reaction temperatures, while keeping all other reaction conditions constant. Three different regions can be clearly distinguished for the two systems: at temperatures <32 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, the observed rate constant increases with temperature, whereas in the region of 32–40 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, K_{app} decreases with increasing temperature, and, finally, at >40 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, the apparent rate constant increases again with temperature (see also Table 1).

As indicated above, the explanation of the observed experimental behavior will be based on the thermoresponsive behavior of the pNIPAM. At temperature below the LCST, pNIPAM is in the swollen state; thus, the reactants can easily diffuse through the pores and reach the Ag surface for both microgel systems. As expected from Arrhenius' law,⁶⁸ the rate constant increased with temperature, from 5.7×10^{-3} to $6.3 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for AuAg@pNIPAM and from 8.3×10^{-3} to $11.2 \times$

10^{-3} s^{-1} for AuAg@pNIPAM@Ag microgel systems. In the vicinity of the LCST ($\sim 32 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$), the particle diameter starts to decrease because of pNIPAM shrinkage. Thus, water molecules are expelled from the microgel network. This decrease in the amount of water molecules affects the diffusion of reactants through the polymer shell, which slows down as the temperature is increased, leading to a decrease in the rate constant from 8.5×10^{-3} to $3.3 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for AuAg@pNIPAM and from 11.3×10^{-3} to $4.7 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for AuAg@pNIPAM@Ag particles. These results indicate that this decrease in the diffusion coefficients is not compensated by the Arrhenius-like increase of the reaction rate with temperature, as occurred below $32 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Once the shell is fully collapsed, the diffusion of reactants is no longer affected by changes in the polymer shell, and further temperature increases again lead to a gradual increase in the rate constant. At $44 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, the K_{app} for AuAg@pNIPAM microgels slightly increased ($3.8 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$) because of typical Arrhenius' behavior. However, the K_{app} value for AuAg@pNIPAM@Ag microgels showed an abrupt increase ($16.4 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$), with the highest rate constant due to the AgSTs immobilised within the pNIPAM shell.

In order to quantitatively compare catalytic activities of different colloidal systems, we include in our investigation a parameter denoted as K_1 , which is the apparent rate constant (K_{app}) normalized to the specific surface area of metal particles (S)

$$-\frac{dC_t}{dt} = k_{\text{app}}C_t = K_1SC_t \quad (2)$$

In our case, we have obtained the surface area of silver by using the same approach previously used by Liz-Marzán et al.⁶⁹

$$S_{\text{Ag}} = 3[\text{Ag}]V_{\text{mAg}}R_{\text{Ag}}^{-1} \quad (3)$$

where $[\text{Ag}]$ is the molar concentration of Ag, V_{mAg} is the molar volume of Ag, and R_{Ag} is the radius of Ag. This allows the quantitative comparison of the catalytic activity of our different hybrid microgels with other systems reported in literature, in which Ag-based systems were used as nanocatalysts for the reduction of 4-Nip. As we are working with bimetallic AuAg systems, the silver concentration was obtained by TGA and EDX-TEM analysis. Figure S7A,B represents the weight loss for both AuAg@pNIPAM and AuAg@pNIPAM@Ag microgels, respectively. For the first system, the amount of bimetallic AuAg obtained after heating the sample at $800 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ is 74%. The percentage of Au and Ag for this colloidal particle was obtained by the EDX spectrum from TEM analysis. Figure S8 shows the EDX spectrum and the table with the percentage of Au and Ag in the AuAg@pNIPAM microgel system. As observed, the percentages of gold and silver were 74.7 and 25.3, respectively. With these data, the calculated Ag surface area was $2.01 \times 10^{-2} \text{ m}^2/\text{L}$. For the AuAg@pNIPAM@Ag system, the TGA analysis resulted in an 86% of bimetallic residue, and the EDX spectrum provided an 85.8% of Ag and a 14.2% of Au. The calculated Ag surface area then was calculated to be $2.75 \times 10^{-2} \text{ m}^2/\text{L}$. Details for the calculation of S_{Ag} are included in the Supporting Information. Table 1 includes the calculated K_1 values for both microgel systems at all investigated temperatures.

Both thermoresponsive catalytic systems exhibited very short induction times at all temperatures as was previously mentioned. The induction time is a typical phenomenon for

the heterogeneous catalysis and related to the time required for the catalyst activation. In the reactions performed in our study, after addition of all the reactants, within the second spectrum run at a time interval of 60 s, the absorbance intensity was already decreased revealing the initiation of the catalytic reaction. This observation can prove that the induction time in our systems was very small because the AgNPs are directly in contact with the reaction components and no time for the diffusion of 4-Nip to reach the surface of metal NPs was needed like in other studies.^{66,67} Bigger induction times are normally attributed to many factors: (i) the diffusion-controlled adsorption of reactants onto the nanoparticle surface as already mentioned, (ii) the presence of dissolved oxygen in water reacting at a faster rate with NaBH_4 than with 4-Nip, (iii) the coating of a metal oxide layer onto the metal surface upon the addition of BH_4^- , poisoning the catalyst surface, and (iv) a slow surface restructuring of the nanoparticles.⁶⁵ However, in our work, the aqueous reaction medium containing the 4-Nip was degassed before adding the NaBH_4 ; therefore, we avoided the formation of an oxide layer at the AgNP surface as well as the reaction of NaBH_4 with dissolved oxygen. Figure 7 shows the mechanisms and forms of

Figure 7. Mechanisms and forms of reduction reaction for 4-Nip to 4-Amp. The photo shows a cuvette containing a mixture of 4-Nip and NaBH_4 before adding the catalytic system (left) and after the catalytic reaction (right) at the end of the reaction (representative image).

reduction reaction toward the transformation of 4-Nip to 4-Amp. In the same figure, two differently colored solutions are observed: one is the yellow color that distinguishes 4-Nip, and the other is the reduced colorless product 4-Amp. The reduction of 4-Nip at all temperatures can be related to the Langmuir-Hinshelwood model of heterogeneous catalyzed reduction.⁷⁰ According to this model, borohydride ions are adsorbed onto the surface of the AgNPs and give them the electrons. At the same time, molecules of 4-Nip adsorbed onto the surface of AgNPs are reduced by these electrons. After reduction, the reaction product 4-Amp is desorbed from the Ag surface. In other words, the addition of NaBH_4 in H_2O results in the appearance of the band at 400 nm because of the 4-nitrophenolate anions formation. At the same time, the NaBH_4 reduces water to hydrogen as shown by the reaction

The reduction reaction is carried out by the hydrogen and involves the production of hydrogen gas that is seen in the form of bubbles. The reaction mechanism can be explained by the inherent hydrogen adsorption by AgNPs, which is efficiently released during the reduction reaction. As such, the AgNPs shuttle the hydrogen transport between NaBH_4 and 4-Nip acting as a hydrogen carrier in this reduction reaction. It

is well known that the applications of MeNPs in the catalytic application depend on the number of metal-atoms on surface of nanoparticle; consequently those containing a larger number of atoms on the surface have more catalytic activity. This explains also the fact that our results are superior to the catalytic performance of CTAB-coated AuNPs encapsulated in pNIPAM shell reported elsewhere.¹

The degradation of Nip is as follows

which can be split into a hydrogen producing and a hydrogen consuming reaction as follows

For the hydrogen producing part, the electron transfer is the most important kinetic factor. It is a surface reaction, which depends on the morphology, surface area, and bimetallic structure of the catalyst, rendering the catalyst an effective electron-relay system.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study presents novel hybrid metal@microgel@metal systems consisting of bimetallic core@shell@satellites particles as highly efficient thermoresponsive catalysts toward the reduction of 4-Nip to 4-Amp. The general process involves the initial fabrication of AuNPs encapsulated with a thermoresponsive microgel. Then, by using AgNO₃ as a silver precursor, a selective growth of a silver shell or Ag satellites can be performed in function of the reducing agent used (AA or NaBH₄). The structure, optical and plasmonic behavior, as well as thermoresponsiveness of the hybrid systems have been demonstrated via TEM, HAAD, EDX, DLS, and UV-vis spectroscopy. The resulting AuAg@pNIPAM and AuAg@pNIPAM@Ag thermoresponsive catalysts have been tested for their catalytic activity via the reduction of 4-Nip to 4-Amp in the presence of NaBH₄. The reaction conforms to the first-order kinetics, and the reaction rate is significantly related to reaction temperature, which makes these systems capable of “temperature-programmable” heterogeneous catalysis.

AUTHOR INFORMATION

Corresponding Authors

*E-mail: fery@ipfdd.de. Phone: +49 351 4658 225 (A.F.).

*E-mail: rcontreras@uma.es, rafcontr@ucm.es. Phone: +34 951234236 (R.C.-C.).

ORCID

Andreas Fery: 0000-0001-6692-3762

Rafael Contreras-Caceres: 0000-0001-6313-2340

Author Contributions

The manuscript was written through contributions of all authors. All authors have given approval for the final version of the manuscript.

Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

J.M.L.-R. and R.C.C. acknowledge financial support from the Spanish MINECO project CTQ2016-76311. R.C.-C. acknowledges funding from the Comunidad de Madrid for the “Atraccion de Talento” project (2018-T1/IND-10736). L.T. gratefully acknowledges the Bodossaki Foundation for financial support. The authors would like to thank A. Caspari for conducting the DLS measurements. The authors are thankful to Adolfo Martinez-Orellana for the 3D tomography analysis.

REFERENCES

- (1) Carregal-Romero, S.; Buurma, N. J.; Pérez-Juste, J.; Liz-Marzán, L. M.; Hervés, P. Catalysis by Au@pNIPAM Nanocomposites: Effect of the Cross-Linking Density. *Chem. Mater.* **2010**, *22*, 3051–3059.
- (2) Tzounis, L.; Contreras-Caceres, R.; Schellkopf, L.; Jehnichen, D.; Fischer, D.; Cai, C.; Uhlmann, P.; Stamm, M. Controlled growth of Ag nanoparticles decorated onto the surface of SiO₂ spheres: a nanohybrid system with combined SERS and catalytic properties. *RSC Adv.* **2014**, *4*, 17846–17855.
- (3) Charisiou, N. D.; Papageridis, K. N.; Tzounis, L.; Sebastian, V.; Hinder, S. J.; Baker, M. A.; AlKetbi, M.; Polychronopoulou, K.; Goula, M. A. Ni supported on CaO-MgO-Al₂O₃ as a highly selective and stable catalyst for H₂ production via the glycerol steam reforming reaction. *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* **2019**, *44*, 256–273.
- (4) Liu, B.; Zhao, X.; Zhu, W.; Luo, W.; Cheng, X. Multiple Pass-Band Optical Left-Handed Metamaterials Based on Random Dendritic Cells. *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2008**, *18*, 3523–3528.
- (5) Rycenga, M.; Cobley, C. M.; Zeng, J.; Li, W.; Moran, C. H.; Zhang, Q.; Qin, D.; Xia, Y. Controlling the Synthesis and Assembly of Silver Nanostructures for Plasmonic Applications. *Chem. Rev.* **2011**, *111*, 3669–3712.
- (6) Kamyshny, A.; Magdassi, S. Conductive Nanomaterials for Printed Electronics. *Small* **2014**, *10*, 3515–3535.
- (7) Kapnopoulos, C.; Mekeridis, E. D.; Tzounis, L.; Polyzoidis, C.; Zachariadis, A.; Tsimikli, S.; Gravalidis, C.; Laskarakis, A.; Vouroutzis, N.; Logothetidis, S. Fully gravure printed organic photovoltaic modules: A straightforward process with a high potential for large scale production. *Sol. Energy Mater. Sol. Cells* **2016**, *144*, 724–731.
- (8) Yan, H.; Melosh, N. Nanoparticles make salty circuits. *Nat. Nanotechnol.* **2016**, *11*, 579–580.
- (9) Edwardson, T. G. W.; Lau, K. L.; Bousmail, D.; Serpell, C. J.; Sleiman, H. F. Transfer of molecular recognition information from DNA nanostructures to gold nanoparticles. *Nat. Chem.* **2016**, *8*, 162–170.
- (10) Saha, K.; Agasti, S. S.; Kim, C.; Li, X.; Rotello, V. M. Gold Nanoparticles in Chemical and Biological Sensing. *Chem. Rev.* **2012**, *112*, 2739–2779.
- (11) Priyadarshini, E.; Pradhan, N. Gold nanoparticles as efficient sensors in colorimetric detection of toxic metal ions: A review. *Sens. Actuators, B* **2017**, *238*, 888–902.

- (12) Alivisatos, A. P. Perspectives on the Physical Chemistry of Semiconductor Nanocrystals. *J. Phys. Chem. A* **1996**, *100*, 13226–13239.
- (13) Kreibitz, U.; Vollmer, M. *Optical Properties of Metal Cluster*; Springer Series in Material Science; Springer, 1995; Vol. 25.
- (14) Link, S.; El-Sayed, M. A. Shape and size dependence of radiative, non-radiative and photothermal properties of gold nanocrystals. *Int. Rev. Phys. Chem.* **2000**, *19*, 409–453.
- (15) Shen, C.; Hui, C.; Yang, T.; Xiao, C.; Tian, J.; Bao, L.; Chen, S.; Ding, H.; Gao, H. Monodisperse Noble-Metal Nanoparticles and Their Surface Enhanced Raman Scattering Properties. *Chem. Mater.* **2008**, *20*, 6939–6944.
- (16) Tana; Wang, F.; Li, H.; Shen, W. Influence of Au particle size on Au/CeO₂ catalysts for CO oxidation. *Catal. Today* **2011**, *175*, 541–545.
- (17) Hervés, P.; Pérez-Lorenzo, M.; Liz-Marzán, L. M.; Dzubielia, J.; Lu, Y.; Ballauff, M. Catalysis by metallic nanoparticles in aqueous solution: model reactions. *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2012**, *41*, 5577–5587.
- (18) Roldan Cuenya, B. Metal Nanoparticle Catalysts Beginning to Shape-up. *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2013**, *46*, 1682–1691.
- (19) Mohanta, J.; Satapathy, S.; Si, S. Porous Silica-Coated Gold Nanorods: A Highly Active Catalyst for the Reduction of 4-Nitrophenol. *ChemPhysChem* **2016**, *17*, 364–368.
- (20) Guria, M. K.; Majumdar, M.; Bhattacharyya, M. Green synthesis of protein capped nano-gold particle: An excellent recyclable nano-catalyst for the reduction of nitro-aromatic pollutants at higher concentration. *J. Mol. Liq.* **2016**, *222*, 549–557.
- (21) Wunder, S.; Lu, Y.; Albrecht, M.; Ballauff, M. Catalytic Activity of Faceted Gold Nanoparticles Studied by a Model Reaction: Evidence for Substrate-Induced Surface Restructuring. *ACS Catal.* **2011**, *1*, 908–916.
- (22) Johnson, J. A.; Makis, J. J.; Marvin, K. A.; Rodenbusch, S. E.; Stevenson, K. J. Size-Dependent Hydrogenation of p-Nitrophenol with Pd Nanoparticles Synthesized with Poly(amido)amine Dendrimer Templates. *J. Phys. Chem. C* **2013**, *117*, 22644–22651.
- (23) Satapathy, S. S.; Bhol, P.; Chakkarambath, A.; Mohanta, J.; Samantaray, K.; Bhat, S. K.; Panda, S. K.; Mohanty, P. S.; Si, S. Thermo-responsive PNIPAM-metal hybrids: An efficient nanocatalyst for the reduction of 4-nitrophenol. *Appl. Surf. Sci.* **2017**, *420*, 753–763.
- (24) Kuttner, C.; Mayer, M.; Dulle, M.; Moscoso, A.; López-Romero, J. M.; Förster, S.; Fery, A.; Pérez-Juste, J.; Contreras-Cáceres, R. Seeded Growth Synthesis of Gold Nanotriangles: Size Control, SAXS Analysis, and SERS Performance. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2018**, *10*, 11152–11163.
- (25) Palioura, D.; Armes, S. P.; Anastasiadis, S. H.; Vamvakaki, M. Metal Nanocrystals Incorporated within pH-Responsive Microgel Particles. *Langmuir* **2007**, *23*, 5761–5768.
- (26) Xiao, C.; Chen, S.; Zhang, L.; Zhou, S.; Wu, W. One-pot synthesis of responsive catalytic Au@PVP hybrid nanogels. *Chem. Commun.* **2012**, *48*, 11751–11753.
- (27) Liu, Z.; Wang, X.; Wu, H.; Li, C. Silver nanocomposite layer-by-layer films based on assembled polyelectrolyte/dendrimer. *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* **2005**, *287*, 604–611.
- (28) Chen, C.-W.; Serizawa, T.; Akashi, M. Synthesis and Characterization of Poly(N-isopropylacrylamide)-Coated Polystyrene Microspheres with Silver Nanoparticles on Their Surfaces†. *Langmuir* **1999**, *15*, 7998–8006.
- (29) Gupta, S.; Agrawal, M.; Conrad, M.; Hutter, N. A.; Olk, P.; Simon, F.; Eng, L. M.; Stamm, M.; Jordan, R. Poly(2-(dimethylamino)ethyl methacrylate) Brushes with Incorporated Nanoparticles as a SERS Active Sensing Layer. *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2010**, *20*, 1756–1761.
- (30) Contreras-Caceres, R.; Dawson, C.; Formanek, P.; Fischer, D.; Simon, F.; Janke, A.; Uhlmann, P.; Stamm, M. Polymers as Templates for Au and Au@Ag Bimetallic Nanorods: UV-Vis and Surface Enhanced Raman Spectroscopy. *Chem. Mater.* **2013**, *25*, 158–169.
- (31) Lu, Y.; Mei, Y.; Drechsler, M.; Ballauff, M. Thermosensitive Core-Shell Particles as Carriers for Ag Nanoparticles: Modulating the Catalytic Activity by a Phase Transition in Networks. *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* **2006**, *45*, 813–816.
- (32) Gupta, S.; Uhlmann, P.; Agrawal, M.; Chapuis, S.; Oertel, U.; Stamm, M. Immobilization of Silver Nanoparticles on Responsive Polymer Brushes. *Macromolecules* **2008**, *41*, 2874–2879.
- (33) Li, J.; Liu, C.-y.; Liu, Y. Au/graphene hydrogel: synthesis, characterization and its use for catalytic reduction of 4-nitrophenol. *J. Mater. Chem.* **2012**, *22*, 8426–8430.
- (34) Praus, P.; Turicová, M.; Karlíková, M.; Kvítek, L.; Dvorský, R. Nanocomposite of montmorillonite and silver nanoparticles: Characterization and application in catalytic reduction of 4-nitrophenol. *Mater. Chem. Phys.* **2013**, *140*, 493–498.
- (35) Shimizu, K.-i.; Miyamoto, Y.; Satsuma, A. Silica-Supported Silver Nanoparticles with Surface Oxygen Species as a Reusable Catalyst for Alkylation of Arenes. *ChemCatChem* **2010**, *2*, 84–91.
- (36) Li, S.; Lin, D.; Zhou, J.; Zha, L. Preparation of Silver Nanoparticles Loaded Photoresponsive Composite Microgels and Their Light-Controllable Catalytic Activity. *J. Phys. Chem. C* **2016**, *120*, 4902–4908.
- (37) Zhang, X.; Zhang, X.; Feng, R.-p.; Liu, L.-h.; Meng, H. Synthesis, characterization and catalytic activity of Au nanoparticles supported on PANI/ α -Fe₂O₃ composite carriers. *Mater. Chem. Phys.* **2012**, *136*, 555–560.
- (38) Mohan, Y. M.; Premkumar, T.; Lee, K.; Geckeler, K. E. Fabrication of Silver Nanoparticles in Hydrogel Networks. *Macromol. Rapid Commun.* **2006**, *27*, 1346–1354.
- (39) Yin, P.-G.; Chen, Y.; Jiang, L.; You, T.-T.; Lu, X.-Y.; Guo, L.; Yang, S. Controlled Dispersion of Silver Nanoparticles into the Bulk of Thermosensitive Polymer Microspheres: Tunable Plasmonic Coupling by Temperature Detected by Surface Enhanced Raman Scattering. *Macromol. Rapid Commun.* **2011**, *32*, 1000–1006.
- (40) Roa, R.; Angioletti-Uberti, S.; Lu, Y.; Dzubielia, J.; Piazza, F.; Ballauff, M. Catalysis by Metallic Nanoparticles in Solution: Thermosensitive Microgels as Nanoreactors. *Z. Phys. Chem.* **2018**, *232*, 773–803.
- (41) Contreras-Cáceres, R.; Pacifico, J.; Pastoriza-Santos, I.; Pérez-Juste, J.; Fernández-Barbero, A.; Liz-Marzán, L. M. Au@pNIPAM Thermosensitive Nanostructures: Control over Shell Cross-linking, Overall Dimensions, and Core Growth. *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2009**, *19*, 3070–3076.
- (42) Fernández-López, C.; Polavarapu, L.; Solís, D. M.; Taboada, J. M.; Obelleiro, F.; Contreras-Cáceres, R.; Pastoriza-Santos, I.; Pérez-Juste, J. Gold Nanorod-pNIPAM Hybrids with Reversible Plasmon Coupling: Synthesis, Modeling, and SERS Properties. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2015**, *7*, 12530–12538.
- (43) Contreras-Cáceres, R.; Sánchez-Iglesias, A.; Karg, M.; Pastoriza-Santos, I.; Pérez-Juste, J.; Pacifico, J.; Hellweg, T.; Fernández-Barbero, A.; Liz-Marzán, L. M. Encapsulation and Growth of Gold Nanoparticles in Thermoresponsive Microgels. *Adv. Mater.* **2008**, *20*, 1666–1670.
- (44) Fernández-López, C.; Pérez-Balado, C.; Pérez-Juste, J.; Pastoriza-Santos, I.; de Lera, Á. R.; Liz-Marzán, L. M. A general LbL strategy for the growth of pNIPAM microgels on Au nanoparticles with arbitrary shapes. *Soft Matter* **2012**, *8*, 4165–4170.
- (45) Pérez-Juste, J.; Pastoriza-Santos, I.; Liz-Marzán, L. M. Multifunctionality in metal@microgel colloidal nanocomposites. *J. Mater. Chem. A* **2013**, *1*, 20–26.
- (46) Lu, Y.; Mei, Y.; Ballauff, M.; Drechsler, M. Thermosensitive Core-Shell Particles as Carrier Systems for Metallic Nanoparticles. *J. Phys. Chem. B* **2006**, *110*, 3930–3937.
- (47) Liu, Y.-Y.; Liu, X.-Y.; Yang, J.-M.; Lin, D.-L.; Chen, X.; Zha, L.-S. Investigation of Ag nanoparticles loading temperature responsive hybrid microgels and their temperature controlled catalytic activity. *Colloids Surf., A* **2012**, *393*, 105–110.
- (48) Lü, J.; Fu, Y.; Song, Y.; Wang, D.; Lü, C. Temperature-dependent catalytic reduction of 4-nitrophenol based on silver nanoclusters protected by a thermo-responsive copolymer ligand. *RSC Adv.* **2016**, *6*, 14247–14252.

- (49) Zhu, C.-H.; Hai, Z.-B.; Cui, C.-H.; Li, H.-H.; Chen, J.-F.; Yu, S.-H. In Situ Controlled Synthesis of Thermosensitive Poly(N-isopropylacrylamide)/Au Nanocomposite Hydrogels by Gamma Radiation for Catalytic Application. *Small* **2012**, *8*, 930–936.
- (50) Lu, Y.; Yuan, J.; Polzer, F.; Drechsler, M.; Preussner, J. In Situ Growth of Catalytic Active Au–Pt Bimetallic Nanorods in Thermoresponsive Core–Shell Microgels. *ACS Nano* **2010**, *4*, 7078–7086.
- (51) Wu, S.; Dzubiella, J.; Kaiser, J.; Drechsler, M.; Guo, X.; Ballauff, M.; Lu, Y. Thermosensitive Au-PNIPA yolk-shell nanoparticles with tunable selectivity for catalysis. *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* **2012**, *51*, 2229–2233.
- (52) Li, L.; Niu, R.; Zhang, Y. Ag–Au bimetallic nanocomposites stabilized with organic–inorganic hybrid microgels: synthesis and their regulated optical and catalytic properties. *RSC Adv.* **2018**, *8*, 12428–12438.
- (53) Li, K.; Chen, X.; Wang, Z.; Xu, L.; Fu, W.; Zhao, L.; Chen, L. Temperature-responsive catalytic performance of Ag nanoparticles endowed by poly (N -isopropylacrylamide-co -acrylic acid) microgels. *Polym. Compos.* **2017**, *38*, 708–718.
- (54) Brändel, T.; Sabadasch, V.; Hannappel, Y.; Hellweg, T. Improved Smart Microgel Carriers for Catalytic Silver Nanoparticles. *ACS Omega* **2019**, *4*, 4636–4649.
- (55) Contreras-Cáceres, R.; Pastoriza-Santos, I.; Alvarez-Puebla, R. A.; Pérez-Juste, J.; Fernández-Barbero, A.; Liz-Marzán, L. M. Growing Au/Ag Nanoparticles within Microgel Colloids for Improved Surface-Enhanced Raman Scattering Detection. *Chem.—Eur. J.* **2010**, *16*, 9462–9467.
- (56) Yang, Z.; Lin, Y.-W.; Tseng, W.-L.; Chang, H.-T. Impacts that pH and metal ion concentration have on the synthesis of bimetallic and trimetallic nanorods from gold seeds. *J. Mater. Chem.* **2003**, *15*, 2450–2454.
- (57) Carbó-Argibay, E.; Rodríguez-González, B.; Pacifico, J.; Pastoriza-Santos, I.; Pérez-Juste, J.; Liz-Marzán, L. M. Chemical sharpening of gold nanorods: the rod-to-octahedron transition. *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* **2007**, *46*, 8983–8987.
- (58) Sepúlveda, B.; Angelomé, P. C.; Lechuga, L. M.; Liz-Marzán, L. M. LSPR-based nanobiosensors. *Nano Today* **2009**, *4*, 244.
- (59) Kreibitz, U.; Vollmer, M. Experimental Results and Discussion. *Optical Properties of Metal Clusters*; Springer Berlin Heidelberg: Berlin, Heidelberg, 1995; pp 275–436.
- (60) Contreras-Cáceres, R.; Abalde-Cela, S.; Guardia-Girós, P.; Fernández-Barbero, A.; Pérez-Juste, J.; Alvarez-Puebla, R. A.; Liz-Marzán, L. M. Multifunctional Microgel Magnetic/Optical Traps for SERS Ultradetection. *Langmuir* **2011**, *27*, 4520–4525.
- (61) Dong, X.; Zou, X.; Liu, X.; Lu, P.; Yang, J.; Lin, D.; Zhang, L.; Zha, L. Temperature-tunable plasmonic property and SERS activity of the monodisperse thermo-responsive composite microgels with core-shell structure based on gold nanorod as core. *Colloids Surf., A* **2014**, *452*, 46–50.
- (62) Zhang, C.; Li, C.; Chen, Y.; Zhang, Y. Synthesis and catalysis of Ag nanoparticles trapped into temperature-sensitive and conductive polymers. *J. Mater. Sci.* **2014**, *49*, 6872–6882.
- (63) Wang, M.-L.; Jiang, T.-T.; Lu, Y.; Liu, H.-J.; Chen, Y. Gold nanoparticles immobilized in hyperbranched polyethylenimine modified polyacrylonitrile fiber as highly efficient and recyclable heterogeneous catalysts for the reduction of 4-nitrophenol. *J. Mater. Chem. A* **2013**, *1*, 5923–5933.
- (64) Gangula, A.; Podila, R.; M, R.; Karanam, L.; Janardhana, C.; Rao, A. M. Catalytic Reduction of 4-Nitrophenol using Biogenic Gold and Silver Nanoparticles Derived from *Breynia rhamnoides*. *Langmuir* **2011**, *27*, 15268–15274.
- (65) Zhang, W.; Tan, F.; Wang, W.; Qiu, X.; Qiao, X.; Chen, J. Facile, template-free synthesis of silver nanodendrites with high catalytic activity for the reduction of p-nitrophenol. *J. Hazard. Mater.* **2012**, *217–218*, 36–42.
- (66) Yuan, J.; Wunder, S.; Warmuth, F.; Lu, Y. Spherical polymer brushes with vinylimidazolium-type poly(ionic liquid) chains as support for metallic nanoparticles. *Polymer* **2012**, *53*, 43–49.
- (67) Signori, A. M.; Santos, K. d. O.; Eising, R.; Albuquerque, B. L.; Giacomelli, F. C.; Domingos, J. B. Formation of Catalytic Silver Nanoparticles Supported on Branched Polyethyleneimine Derivatives. *Langmuir* **2010**, *26*, 17772–17779.
- (68) Carregal-Romero, S.; Pérez-Juste, J.; Hervés, P.; Liz-Marzán, L. M.; Mulvaney, P. Colloidal Gold-Catalyzed Reduction of Ferrocyanate (III) by Borohydride Ions: A Model System for Redox Catalysis. *Langmuir* **2010**, *26*, 1271–1277.
- (69) Liz-Marzán, L. M.; Giersig, M.; Mulvaney, P. Synthesis of Nanosized Gold-Silica Core-Shell Particle. *Langmuir* **1996**, *12*, 4329–4335.
- (70) Khalavka, Y.; Becker, J.; Sönnichsen, C. Synthesis of Rod-Shaped Gold Nanorattles with Improved Plasmon Sensitivity and Catalytic Activity. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2009**, *131*, 1871–1875.